

XMR: Exact Match Recovery for Evaluating Text Normalization Against Adversarial Unicode Attacks

Version 2. The headline score, re-measured over a broad sample of the cross-script and compatibility confusable space.

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Abstract

Exact Match Recovery (XMR) is a metric for evaluating text normalization pipelines as defences against adversarial Unicode attacks. It measures whether a preprocessing function maps attacked and clean text to the same output, without downstream model inference. Version 1 of this note defined the metric. The version 1 benchmark, previously unpublished and released with this deposit, reported a score of 1.000 for translit (visual TR39 confusable mapping), measured against a homoglyph attack drawn from 18 hand-curated Cyrillic lookalike pairs over 1,000 SST-2 snippets, while phonetic transliterators reached 0.487 and no-op baselines 0.101. That pair set is a small part of the Unicode TR39 confusable space, which defines mappings for 6,565 source characters. This version re-runs the same benchmark on the same corpus with the same metric, changing only the attack: it is extended to the 1,314 single-codepoint sources whose TR39 skeleton is a single Latin letter, reported over two nested cuts, a 797-source compatibility subset and the 517-source cross-script remainder. Two mapping-table baselines are added, NFKC and the TR39 skeleton transform itself. The benchmark reproduces every version 1 score exactly on the curated attack. On the broad sample, translit falls to 0.634 (strip_obfuscation; 95 percent CI 0.603 to 0.664) and 0.682 (full pipeline; CI 0.652 to 0.710). A per-source probe separates coverage from compounding: translit neutralizes 95 percent of the 1,314 sources (0.949 and 0.954 per pipeline), and the lower instance scores follow from the unrecovered 5 percent compounding across the several substitutions each snippet carries. The TR39 skeleton transform scores 1.000 on the broad sample by construction; it shares its table with the attack and serves as the oracle ceiling rather than as a competitor. NFKC reaches only 0.103, because compatibility folding restores each character to its nominal letter, which is often not the Latin letter the attacker replaced. The phonetic transliterators stay at or below 0.187. The recommendation stands: measure the headline number over the full confusable space, report it per region, and report per-source coverage alongside instance XMR. Disclosure: translit is developed by the author.

1. Motivation

Boucher et al. (2022) showed that imperceptible Unicode perturbations, including homoglyph substitutions, invisible character injections, and reorderings, can break deployed NLP classifiers, including commercial systems. Eger et al. (2019) demonstrated the same fragility for visual perturbations more broadly and explored shielding methods, including rule-based recovery, the defence class measured here. The visual confusability itself has a longer history in identifier spoofing: Holgers et al. (2006) measured homograph attacks on internationalized domain names, where a Cyrillic letter standing in for a Latin one produces a deceptive address. In the wild, Cooper, Surdeanu, and Blanco (2023) collected ninety thousand tweets in which hate speech was masked by homoglyphs, and found that normalization restored detector performance. A common defence applies a text normalization step before tokenization, resolving or stripping adversarial characters before they reach the model. Bitton et al. (2022) proposed an adversarial text normalizer measured through downstream task accuracy, and Cooper, Blanco, and Surdeanu (2025) applied large language models to the same problem. XMR isolates the preprocessing step from model inference, which allows faster iteration and fairer comparison across tools.

The version 1 note (Quinn, 2026) defined XMR. The accompanying benchmark reported a single headline score: translit, using visual TR39 confusable mapping, achieved XMR equal to 1.000, while phonetic transliterators plateaued at 0.487. This version examines whether that score holds when the attack is drawn from the broad confusable space rather than the curated pairs on which it was measured.

2. What the version 1 score measured

The version 1 benchmark has not previously been published; the version 1 note defined the metric only. The benchmark code and a summary of its results are released with this deposit (e1_xmr_benchmark.py, attacks.py, tools.py, e1_homoglyph_summary.json), and every version 1 number quoted in this note is reproduced by the present run. Its homoglyph attack substituted Latin characters using a curated map of 18 Cyrillic Latin-lookalikes (a separate experiment added 19 Greek pairs). translit carries a TR39 confusable table that covers those pairs, so it reverses the substitutions and scores 1.000. The question this version asks is whether that score is a property of translit across the confusable space, or a property of the curated attack: the 18 pairs are a small part of the 6,565 source characters that confusables.txt maps.

One point of interpretation carries over unchanged. XMR compares $P(C(t))$ to $P(t)$, the tool's output on attacked text against its output on clean text. It certifies that the model receives the same input it would have received without the attack. It does not certify that the original byte string was reconstructed; for translit, which leaves clean ASCII unchanged, the two coincide, so the distinction does not affect the scores reported here.

3. Method

This version reuses the version 1 benchmark, changing only the attack.

Comparators. The eight tools from the version 1 benchmark: none (identity), ftfy (encoding repair), unicode, anyascii, cyrtranslit, and uroman (phonetic transliterators), and translit through its strip_obfuscation and full pipelines (translit-rs 0.6.3). Disclosure: translit is developed by the author; it is measured by the same public harness as every baseline, and the harness is released. Version 2 adds two mapping-table baselines. nfkc applies the standard library compatibility fold. tr39_skeleton applies the UTS #39 skeleton transform built from the same confusables.txt the attack samples from; it is not a deployable normalizer (it rewrites clean text aggressively, mapping every m to rn for instance, which the metric forgives because both sides receive it), and it is included as the oracle row: the score available to a tool whose confusable table equals the attack's.

Metric. The version 1 XMR: for an evaluation corpus T , a corruption function C , and a preprocessing function P ,

$$\text{XMR}(P, C, T) = (1 / |T|) \sum_{t \text{ in } T} \text{of } 1[\text{NFC}(P(C(t))) = \text{NFC}(P(t))]$$

The NFC wrap is an addition to the version 1 formula; it is a no-op on the ASCII outputs here and is stated for completeness. The metric uses NFC rather than NFKC, so folding of compatibility characters is left to the tool under test rather than performed by the comparison. Character Error Rate is reported alongside for context, computed as in version 1: the Levenshtein (1966) edit distance between $P(C(t))$ and $P(t)$, normalized by the longer of the two.

Attack. Homoglyph substitution at rate 0.30 per eligible character, swept over 0.15 and 0.45 as a sensitivity check. Four cuts of the confusable space:

- R1 curated: the version 1 homoglyph attack, applied through the version 1 attack code (attacks.py) with its original seeding, so the R1 column reproduces the version 1 benchmark exactly.
- R2 broad: every single-codepoint source whose TR39 skeleton is a single Latin letter, 1,314 sources. They cover 50 of the 52 ASCII letters: no source skeletonizes to capital I or to m, because TR39 maps capital I lookalikes to lowercase I and m lookalikes to the two-character sequence rn.
- R2 cross-script: the 517 sources of R2 outside R3, dominated by Cyrillic, Greek, and other script lookalikes.
- R3 compatibility: the fullwidth (U+FF01 to U+FF5E) and mathematical-alphanumeric (U+1D400 to U+1D7FF) subset of R2, 797 sources, isolated because NFKC targets exactly these blocks. R2 cross-script and R3 partition R2.

Corpus. The version 1 corpus, unchanged: 1,000 snippets from the SST-2 training split, selected with seed 42 (the selection is `rng = Random(42); sorted(sample(range(67349), 1000))`), cached in `sst2_v1_corpus.json` and released with this deposit so the run needs no network access. Corpus, metric, and comparators are the version 1 benchmark's; the attack is the only experimental variable. `uroman` romanizes at about 85 ms per string; it is evaluated on the first 120 instances of the corpus with a shared clean-output cache and is excluded from the seed and rate sweeps. Version 1 evaluated `uroman` on the full corpus; its subsample score on R1 here (0.467, n equal to 120) is consistent with its full-corpus version 1 score (0.487). The data source is `Unicode confusables.txt` version 17.0.0.

Uncertainty. Every cell carries a 95 percent percentile bootstrap interval over instances (B equal to 2,000, seeded). The corruption is redrawn under four additional seeds (43 to 46) for every tool except `uroman`; the seed ranges are narrow, for example 0.682 to 0.693 for the full pipeline on R2. All corruption, sampling, and bootstrap draws are deterministic given the released seeds.

Per-source probe. For every tool and every R2 source character, a single-substitution probe embeds the source in a fixed carrier sentence and compares the tool's output, NFC-wrapped, against its output on the carrier containing the skeleton letter. This yields the source-level coverage statistic that instance-level XMR does not measure: the fraction of the 1,314 sources the tool neutralizes in isolation.

4. Results

XMR (higher is better):

tool	R1 curated	R2 broad	R2 cross-script	R3 compatibility
none	0.101	0.014	0.013	0.012
fffy	0.101	0.016	0.013	0.013
unidecode	0.487	0.133	0.031	0.326
anyascii	0.487	0.187	0.052	0.496
cyrtranslit	0.487	0.014	0.013	0.012
uroman	0.467	0.125	0.033	0.367
translit_strip_obfusc	1.000	0.634	0.497	0.738
translit_full_pipeline	1.000	0.682	0.658	0.738
nfkc	0.101	0.103	0.019	0.319

tr39_skeleton	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
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uroman is measured on 120 instances; all other cells on 1,000.

Character Error Rate (lower is better), for context:

tool	R1 curated	R2 broad	R2 cross-script	R3 compatibility
none	0.086	0.236	0.212	0.236
ftfy	0.086	0.231	0.212	0.228
unidecode	0.018	0.087	0.176	0.046
anyascii	0.018	0.063	0.151	0.018
cyrtranslit	0.018	0.234	0.203	0.236
uroman	0.021	0.113	0.179	0.084
translit_strip_obfusc	0.000	0.014	0.023	0.008
translit_full_pipeline	0.000	0.013	0.015	0.008
nfkc	0.086	0.086	0.192	0.033
tr39_skeleton	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Per-source coverage (fraction of region sources neutralized in the single-substitution probe):

tool	R2 broad	R2 cross-script	R3 compatibility
none	0.001	0.002	0.000
ftfy	0.024	0.002	0.038
unidecode	0.566	0.164	0.827
anyascii	0.675	0.315	0.908
cyrtranslit	0.008	0.019	0.000
uroman	0.580	0.190	0.833
translit_strip_obfusc	0.949	0.923	0.966
translit_full_pipeline	0.954	0.936	0.966
nfkc	0.533	0.081	0.826
tr39_skeleton	1.000	1.000	1.000

XMR on R2 broad under the substitution-rate sweep:

tool	0.15	0.30	0.45
translit_strip_obfusc	0.763	0.634	0.501
translit_full_pipeline	0.802	0.682	0.555
nfkc	0.251	0.103	0.044
tr39_skeleton	1.000	1.000	1.000
anyascii	0.362	0.187	0.107

Five readings follow.

The benchmark reproduces version 1 exactly. Every version 1 comparator reproduces its version 1 homoglyph score on R1 to the third decimal: 1.000 for both translit pipelines, 0.487 for the phonetic transliterators, 0.101 for the no-op baselines, with uroman at 0.467 on its disclosed subsample against 0.487 at full n in version 1. Corpus, metric, and comparator behaviour are unchanged; the columns to the right vary only the attack.

The instance score is region-bound, and the per-source coverage explains it. On the broad sample R2, translit falls to 0.634 for strip_obfuscation (CI 0.603 to 0.664) and 0.682 for the full pipeline (CI 0.652 to 0.710), and scores 0.738 on the compatibility cut R3 (CI 0.711 to 0.764). The per-source probe shows why the instance numbers sit where they do: strip_obfuscation neutralizes 1,247 of the 1,314 R2 sources (0.949) and the full pipeline 1,254 (0.954). An instance fails on a single unrecovered substitution, and at rate 0.30 a snippet carries several substitutions, so a roughly 5 percent per-source gap compounds into the roughly one-third instance failure rate observed. The unneutralized sources (67 and 60 respectively) are listed by codepoint in the released results file. CER stays low throughout for both pipelines (at most 0.023 on any region), so the residual failures are single-character residues rather than wholesale corruption.

The mapping-table baselines bound the space from both ends. tr39_skeleton scores 1.000 on R2, its cuts, and R1 by construction: the attack and the skeleton share confusables.txt, so the row is the oracle ceiling rather than a competitor, and its value is showing the ceiling is reachable by table coverage alone. NFKC, the obvious standard-library candidate for the compatibility region, reaches only 0.319 on R3 and 0.103 on R2. The reason is that compatibility folding restores a character to its nominal letter, while TR39 confusability tracks what the character looks like: 139 of the 797 R3 sources fold to a letter other than their TR39 skeleton, principally mathematical Greek capitals, which NFKC folds to Greek letters rather than to the Latin letters they imitate, and the fullwidth and mathematical capital I forms, which NFKC folds to I where the attack substituted them for I. A fold that returns the wrong nominal letter does not recover the attacked text.

The phonetic transliterators do not close the gap. No phonetic tool exceeds 0.187 on R2, and all fall near zero on the cross-script cut (at most 0.052), because phonetic transliteration maps a Cyrillic or Greek lookalike to its sound rather than to the Latin letter it imitates. Their per-source coverage on R3 is respectable (0.827 to 0.908), which their instance scores on R3 (0.326 to 0.496) again understate through compounding. ffty, an encoding-repair tool, is indistinguishable from doing nothing on confusable attacks.

The ordering is stable under the rate sweep. Lowering the substitution rate to 0.15 or raising it to 0.45 moves every tool's magnitude monotonically, as the compounding argument predicts, and changes no ordering: the skeleton ceiling stays at 1.000, translit stays far above every deployable baseline, and NFKC and the phonetic tools decay toward zero. The headline magnitudes are rate-dependent; the conclusions are not.

5. Discussion

The version 1 score is reproducible and correctly computed, and translit does reach 1.000 on the curated region, well ahead of every baseline. The qualification is coverage: the 18 curated pairs are a small part of the 6,565-source confusable space, and on the broad sample translit's instance scores are 0.634 to 0.738. A reader should not take the single headline number as evidence of recovery across the confusable space.

For practitioners selecting a defence, translit remains the strongest deployable tool measured, by a wide margin, on every region: the next best deployable score on R2 is anyascii at 0.187 against translit's 0.682. The per-source statistic locates the shortfall precisely: 60 of 1,314 sources are not neutralized by the full pipeline, and extending the shipped confusable table toward the full TR39 set

is the entire path between 0.954 coverage and the skeleton's 1.000 ceiling. For evaluation methodology, the recommendation is threefold: measure XMR against the full confusable space rather than a curated subset, report it per region, and report per-source coverage alongside instance XMR, since the instance metric compounds per-source gaps and a tool can score 1.000 on a curated region while a twentieth of the broad space remains unmapped.

6. Limitations

The evaluation covers English source text from one corpus of short snippets, and single-codepoint homoglyph substitution at swept but fixed rates. Multi-character visual confusions and confusions internal to the ASCII range, such as the letter l against the digit 1, are not measured. The per-source probe uses a single fixed carrier sentence; context-dependent normalization behaviour would not register. The evaluation does not include downstream task accuracy; XMR certifies that the model receives the same input as the clean case, not that its prediction is correct. uroman is evaluated on a 120-instance subsample for runtime, with the wide interval that n implies (CI 0.067 to 0.183 on R2). The attack is drawn from the same table that defines the tr39_skeleton baseline, which is why that row is reported as a ceiling rather than as a competing tool; a benchmark drawn from a different confusable inventory would move every number. translit is the author's tool, and the safeguard offered is reproducibility: the harness, corpus, seeds, and per-source results are all released.

7. Reproducibility

Everything is released with this deposit: the experiment script (`xmr_v2_experiment.py`), the cached version 1 corpus (`sst2_v1_corpus.json`), the version 1 comparator and attack code (`tools.py`, `attacks.py`), the version 1 benchmark script and its homoglyph results (`e1_xmr_benchmark.py`, `e1_homoglyph_summary.json`), the result file with bootstrap intervals, seed ranges, and per-source coverage including the unneutralized codepoints (`xmr_v2_results.json`), and the data file (`confusables.txt`, version 17.0.0). translit is translit-rs 0.6.3, available on PyPI with source at github.com/raeq/translit. All scores are computed by string comparison over deterministic, seeded corruption; the corruption seeds, bootstrap seeds, and corpus selection are stated in the script.

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